

Allen in the first days of Run 3

THOMAS BOETTCHER

*On behalf of the LHCb collaboration,
Department of Physics
University of Cincinnati, United States*

ABSTRACT

The LHCb collaboration recently began commissioning an upgraded detector that will be read out at the full 30 MHz LHC event rate. Events will be reconstructed and selected in real time using a GPU-based software trigger called Allen. In this talk, I'll present the status of Allen and discuss how it is evolving as Run 3 begins. In particular, I'll focus on the process of preparing Allen to confront real data and discuss our experiences operating a GPU-based trigger in the early days of Run 3.

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1 Introduction

The primary goal of the LHCb experiment is to study decays of hadrons containing charm and bottom quarks. Figure 1 shows event rates for various Standard Model production processes at the LHC experiments in Run 3. The trigger systems of the ATLAS and CMS experiments are primarily designed to select high-energy signatures of relatively rare processes. These signatures, which include calorimeter clusters with high transverse energy (E_T) and high-momentum muon tracks, can be efficiently identified and selected using hardware-level information from single subdetector subsystems. In contrast, the b and c hadrons studied at LHCb will be produced at rates of $\mathcal{O}(1 \text{ MHz})$. Furthermore, heavy flavor hadrons decay to final-state particles with momenta similar to those of particles from the underlying event. The signature of a heavy flavor hadron decay is a decay vertex (secondary vertex) displaced from the pp collision (primary vertex). Reconstructing a displaced secondary vertex requires global information from LHCb's full charged particle tracking system. As a result, heavy flavor hadrons cannot be efficiently selected using hardware-level triggers. This is demonstrated in Figure 2, which shows the projected performance of an emulated hardware trigger at LHCb in Run 3. At a throughput of 1 MHz, hadronic b -hadron decays are selected with about 10% efficiency, while hadronic c -hadron decays are selected with about 5% efficiency. To solve this challenge, the LHCb collaboration is analyzing the full LHC event rate in real time using a software trigger.

Figure 1: Event rate estimates for various Standard Model processes at the LHC in Run 3 [1].

Figure 2: Selection performance of a hypothetical Run 3 low-level trigger that selects events based on the presence of a single high- E_T HCAL cluster [2].

The LHCb software trigger is split into two stages called “HLT1” and “HLT2”. Data is read out from the detector at an event rate of about 30 MHz and passed to HLT1. HLT1 selects events at a rate of about 1 MHz, which are then passed on for further processing. The LHCb HLT1 has been implemented on GPUs in the Allen software package [3, 4]. Allen is the first complete high-throughput GPU trigger for a high-energy physics experiment. In this contribution, I’ll show how Allen has evolved from a prototype to an operational software trigger over the last two years. I’ll also present some of Allen’s new features and discuss how the Allen team is approaching the challenges of collecting real data as Run 3 begins.

2 The Allen Project

Allen is LHCb’s GPU-based first level software trigger. Named for Frances E. Allen, Allen is available as both a standalone application and as part of the LHCb software stack. Allen can be built for CPUs and GPUs. Both NVIDIA and AMD GPUs are supported using the CUDA and HIP frameworks, respectively.

Allen was originally designed to perform a partial reconstruction of charged particles in HLT1 as described in Ref. [2]. The upgraded LHCb detector is shown in Figure 3 with the subdetectors used in the baseline reconstruction sequence highlighted. Allen must decode data from the Vertex Locator (VELO) [5], Upstream Tracker (UT) [6], Scintillating Fibre (SciFi) [6], and Muon [7] detectors and cluster this data into hits. VELO hits are used to create tracks using the Search by Triplet algorithm [8]. VELO tracks are then propagated to the UT and VELO-UT tracks are constructed using the Compass algorithm [9]. VELO-UT tracks are then extrapolated to the SciFi and are used to define windows to search for SciFi tracks. Reconstructed VELO-UT-SciFi tracks are then extrapolated to the Muon detector stations, which are used to identify muons [10]. The VELO segments of reconstructed tracks are fit using a parameterized Kalman filter [3] and are used to reconstruct secondary vertices. Events are selected based on the properties of tracks and secondary vertices. In addition, Allen also decodes and reconstructs data from the electromagnetic calorimeter (ECAL).

Figure 3: The upgraded LHCb detector. The detector systems used in the baseline HLT1 reconstruction sequence described in Ref. [2] are highlighted in color.

The Run 3 LHCb data acquisition pipeline is shown in Figure 4. The Allen implementation of HLT1 will run on GPUs placed on Event Builder nodes, resulting in a large decrease of data volume transferred between the Event Builder nodes and the CPU farm where HLT2 runs. Furthermore, GPUs can provide more computing power per unit cost than CPUs. Consequently, a GPU-based HLT1 offers many opportunities for cost savings [13]. In addition, Allen is fast enough to allow for additional features to be added to the

HLT1 reconstruction sequence. Because of these cost savings and the potential to expand LHCb’s physics program, the LHCb collaboration adopted Allen as its first level software trigger for Run 3.

Figure 4: Sketch of the LHCb data acquisition system for Run 3, including the GPU-based HLT1 [11]. All numbers related to the dataflow are taken from Refs. [2] and [12].

3 New features in Allen

Many LHCb analyses require reconstructing and identifying electrons. Electrons are identified using the ECAL, which was not used in HLT1 in Runs 1 and 2. ECAL reconstruction has now been implemented in Allen. This includes decoding data from the ECAL, clustering ECAL cells, and matching ECAL clusters to charged tracks. In addition, VELO track trajectories are used to match electron candidates to ECAL clusters produced by bremsstrahlung radiation. ECAL reconstruction will improve Allen’s ability to select final states including electrons and photons such as those used in studies of lepton flavor universality [14] and direct searches for new particles [15, 16].

Most events selected by Allen are selected using inclusive one- and two-track selection algorithms based on neural network (NN) classifiers. These inclusive NNs are trained using simulated heavy flavor decays to select displaced and high-momentum tracks and secondary vertices. Very little training signal is available at large decay times, and backgrounds can be produced by particles interacting with the detector material. As a result, NN performance tends to suffer for particles with large decay times, as shown in Figure 5. To overcome this limitation, methods have been developed to constrain classifiers to produce monotonically increasing responses in a given set of variables [17]. In addition, detector conditions may fluctuate during data taking. In Runs 1 and 2, LHCb accounted for this by discretizing variables used as inputs to selection algorithms [18]. A similar effect can be achieved by limiting the gradient of the classifier response. This has been implemented in so-called “Lipschitz NNs” [17]. The performance of an unconstrained NN is compared to a monotonic BDT and a monotonic Lipschitz NN in Figure 5. The one- and two-track inclusive selections in Allen now both use monotonic Lipschitz NNs.

When Allen was adopted for use in Run 3 in 2020, it had achieved throughput of about 70 kHz on a GeForce RTX 2080 Ti GPU [3]. Allen has achieved dramatic speedups since then, which are due to detailed profiling of GPU occupancy and improvements in compiler configuration. Figure 6 shows updated throughput measurements. When the new features discussed above are included, Allen has still achieved speedups of around 50% on the same card since 2020.

Figure 5: Selection efficiency as a function of decay time for (left) an example unconstrained NN, (middle) a boosted decision tree classifier constrained to have a monotonically increasing performance as a function of decay time, and (right) a NN constrained to have a monotonic response and to satisfy a Lipschitz condition that limits the magnitude of its gradient. From Ref. [17]

Figure 6: Allen throughput on various GPUs and CPUs.

4 Early data taking challenges

The entire LHCb tracking system has been replaced for Run 3. The UT is not expected to be in place until December. The UT provides a charge determination and an initial momentum estimate for charged tracks that can be used to define search windows for hits in the SciFi. Reconstructing tracks without the UT required the development of new tracking algorithms. Two such algorithms have been implemented in Allen and are described in Ref. [19].

In addition to pp collisions, LHCb will simultaneously record data in fixed target mode using the System for Measuring the Overlap with Gas (SMOG) [20]. Figure 7 shows the VELO tracking efficiency as a function of the primary vertex position along the beam axis. Allen is able to simultaneously reconstruct pp and p-gas events with negligible loss of performance.

Allen will also be used to collect PbPb data in November, 2022. Figure 8 shows the LHCb tracking efficiency for charged particles traversing both the VELO and SciFi detectors as a function of the number

Figure 7: VELO tracking efficiency as a function of primary vertex z position for various pp and SMOG2 data-taking scenarios [21]. The pp interaction region is centered at $z = 0$, while the SMOG2 cell is centered near $z = -400$ mm.

of hits in the SciFi detector. In the high-occupancy environment of PbPb collisions, the SciFi detector will saturate, leading to poor tracking performance. As a result, Allen will need to use a new trigger strategy for PbPb data taking, which is currently under development.

Figure 8: SciFi track reconstruction efficiency as a function of the number of hits in the SciFi for reconstructible tracks [21].

5 First data

Allen has been fully integrated into the LHCb data acquisition system using RTX A5000 GPUs and was used to collect cosmic ray data based on ECAL activity beginning in May. Since the end of May, Allen has been used to select pp collisions data. A histogram of selected bunch crossing IDs from pp collisions is shown in Figure 9. The histogram shows sharp peaks corresponding to filled LHC bunches. This demonstrates

that Allen is successfully selecting real pp collisions. Since early July, Allen has processed data from $\sqrt{s} = 13.6$ TeV pp collisions. To date, Allen has processed pp collisions at an event rate of about 27 MHz. Figure 10 shows the Allen selection rate for events with at least one ECAL cluster with E_T of at least 400 MeV.

Figure 9: Histogram of bunch crossing IDs selected by Allen based on ECAL activity in $\sqrt{s} = 900$ pp collisions.

Figure 10: Allen selection rate of $\sqrt{s} = 13.6$ TeV pp events with a single ECAL cluster with $E_T > 400$ MeV. The horizontal axis shows elapsed time in seconds, and the vertical axis shows the selection rate in Hz.

6 Conclusions

Since its adoption as the official LHCb HLT1 software implementation, Allen has grown from a prototype to a fully functional software trigger system. In the meantime, Allen's throughput has increased even as additional features have been added. The LHC just began producing pp collisions at the nominal center-of-mass energy of 13.6 TeV in July, so the challenges and excitement of operating a fully GPU-based software trigger are just beginning.

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